

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18979793](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18979793)

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Performance evaluation of the LISA Radiation Monitor</i>
Project TA identifier	TA13-419
General application	<i>Scientific space mission</i>
Type of test	<i>Radiation monitor calibration</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Daniel Guberman, Institute of Cosmos Science, University of Barcelona (ICCUB)</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Albert Espiña (ICCUB), Marina Orta (ICCUB), Pierpaolo Loizzo (INFN Bari), Roberta Pillera (INFN Bari)</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	26/10/2026 - 27/10/2026
Facility	TRIUMF
Amount of access granted	12 h

Objectives of the experiments

The goal was to characterize the response of a prototype of the LISA Radiation Monitor, designed to detect protons in the range from 100 MeV to 1 GeV. TRIUMF was the best suited facility, mainly due to its energy range.

Experiment test report

The LISA Radiation Monitor

The LISA Radiation Monitor (RM) consists of four plastic scintillators (20x20x3 mm³) separated by three tungsten absorbers (10, 20 and 40 mm thick). Each plastic scintillator is readout by 4 silicon photomultipliers (SiPMs). The SiPM signals are readout and digitized by a readout board based on the BETA ASIC. An FPGA is used for controlling the ASIC and managing the trigger.

Experimental Methods

We mounted the RM in a rotation stage we could control remotely (Figure 1). A scintillator detector provided by TRIUMF was placed between the RM and the beam and was used for triggering. We could eventually place absorber blocks of steel and aluminum between the beam and the scintillator to reduce the energy of the proton beam.

Figure 1: The RM, mounted on the rotation stage, facing the beam collimator output.

We were able to measure the response of the Radiation Monitor to proton energies from ~100 MeV to ~480 MeV by changing the beam line (two lines are available: 480 and 355 MeV) and the aluminum/steel absorber thickness. This way we could achieve eight different beam energies.

We also characterized its angular response at 480 MeV. To do so we moved the rotation stage and took data at different angles, from 0 to 60 degrees.

Preliminary Results

Figure 2 shows the response of the first scintillator (S0) to protons of different energies. As expected, lower-energy protons deposit more energy in the scintillator, leaving a larger signal in ADC cts. Figure 3 shows the most-probable value (MPV) of each of the distributions of Figure 2 as a function of the beam energy, where it can be seen that they agree reasonably well with the expectations from the Bethe-Bloch formula.

Figure 2: Signal measured by the first scintillator (S0) in ADC counts to proton beams of different energies.

Figure 3: Mean number of ADC counts measured by S0 as a function of the beam energy. Solid yellow line: prediction from Bethe-Bloch formula

Figure 4 shows the measured angular response of the coincidence channels (i.e., event that triggered at least two scintillators).

Figure 4: Angular response of the coincidence channels

All the results presented here are very preliminary. The analysis is ongoing and being contrasted with dedicated simulations. The beam time was sufficient and we could take the data we needed. The preliminary results are matching our expectations.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008126.

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/radnext>